

Entrepreneurial Prospectives and Practices

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Abstract

Entrepreneurial marketing is a term which is receiving increasing use. It essentially encompasses two very distinct areas of management: marketing and entrepreneurship. This article is dedicated to exploring the emergence of this area of theory, its history and the current developments in the interface between these two areas. Scholars from both the worlds of marketing and entrepreneurship have long identified similarities in the key issues concerning both. Recent years have seen the emergence of increased study in the area of overlap between the two disciplines. Academics working in this field are undertaking research in a number of key areas, namely entrepreneurial management, networking and the resource and skills implications of adopting an entrepreneurial approach to marketing activities. This research has now built up into a sizeable body of literature and this article introduces the reader to the essence of this research and identifies its usefulness in viewing many areas of management.

Introduction

An entrepreneur perceives a need and then brings together the manpower, materials and capital required to meet that need. Entrepreneurs search for change, respond to it and exploit it as an opportunity. Entrepreneurship involves combining factors of production to initiate changes and it is a discontinuous phenomenon. On the other hand, management involves continual combining and ongoing coordination of productive factors.

Several economic and noneconomic factors affect entrepreneurship. Economic factors include market incentives (new social needs the entrepreneur can attempt to satisfy in new ways) and availability of capital to start and operate new enterprises. Non economic factors consist of

- Political ideology and legal structure which promote free enterprises,
- Social mobility, for example the caste structure in India, restricted social mobility of people and people born in a specific caste confined themselves to particular economic functions,
- Psychological factors like need achievement (people with high need for achievement are more likely to become entrepreneurs),
- Competence, attitudes alone to not make an entrepreneur and ability to compete effectively is necessary, and
- Cultural factors.

Entrepreneurial culture implies a set of values, norms and traits that are conducive to the growth of entrepreneurship. It is the corporate culture that focuses on the emergence of new opportunities, the means of capitalizing on them, and the creation of the structure appropriate for pursuing them. Entrepreneurial culture should be differentiated from administrative culture. Administrative culture is the corporate culture which focuses on existing opportunities, organizational structures and control procedures.

Role and Importance of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is the spirit of a person. It is a quality which may be inherent or developed. For the economic development of a country, entrepreneurial skills need to be developed. These skills lead the development of business and ultimately, the result is seen in the economic growth of the country.

Entrepreneurship Plays A Very Important Role In Terms Of

- Generation of employment opportunities
- Its size and nature, it is more dynamic, flexible and capable of making quick decisions.
- Ensuring balanced economic development. Small enterprises need relatively low investment and can be easily undertaken in rural and semi-urban areas. Starting such enterprises create additional employment in rural areas and prevent migration of people from rural to urban areas. Small enterprises use local resources and are best suited for rural and under developed sectors. Entrepreneurial development accelerates the growth of small firms in India. A number of small firms are expected to be more innovative and make the Indian industry compete in the international market effectively.

The advantages of entrepreneurial development are that it leads to freedom, flexibility, growth and development. It also develops leadership quality.

Objectives of EDPS

The important objectives of the Entrepreneurship development programs (EDPS) are to:

- Develop and strengthen their entrepreneurial quality, i.e., motivation or need for achievement,
- Analyze environmental set up relating to small industry and small business.
- Select product.
- Formulate project for the product.
- Understand the process and procedure involved in setting up a small enterprise.
- Know the sources of help and support available for starting a small-scale industry.
- Acquire the necessary managerial skills required to run a small enterprise.
- Know the pros and cons in becoming an entrepreneur.
- Appreciate the needed entrepreneurial discipline.

Besides, some of the other important objectives of the EDPs are to:

- Let the entrepreneur himself/herself set or reset objectives for his/her business and strive for their realization.
- Prepare him/her to accept the uncertainty involved in running a business.
- Enable him/her to take decisions.
- Enable to communicate clearly and effectively.
- Develop a broad vision about the business.
- Make him subscribe to industrial democracy.
- Develop passion for integrity and honesty.
- Make him learn compliance with law.

Characteristics of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is a multi- dimensional concept and it is necessary to consider many factors and perspectives. The distinctive features of entrepreneurship are summarized below:

Innovation

According to Schumpeter, entrepreneurship is a creative activity. An entrepreneur is basically an innovator who introduces something new into the economy. Entrepreneurial role involves doing things in a new and better way. A businessman, who simply behaves in traditional ways, cannot be an entrepreneur.

A Function of High Achievement

McClelland identified two characteristics of entrepreneurship, namely 'doing things in a new and better way' and decision making under uncertainty'. He stressed the need for achievement or achievement orientation as the most directly relevant factor for explaining economic behaviour.

A Function of Group Level Pattern

Accepting Schumpeter's definition, young suggests a casual sequence where "transformation" are developed by the solidarity group to improve their symbolic position in their larger structure and become entrepreneurs.

Young's theory is a theory of change based on society's incorporation of reactive subgroups. A group becomes reactive when the following three conditions coincide:

- When a group experience low status recognition;
- When denied of access to important social networks; and
- When the group has better institutional resources than other than other groups in the society at the same level.

Gap Filling Function

Liebenstein identified two broad types of entrepreneurship. The 'routine entrepreneurship' is associated with the managerial function of the business where as the 'new entrepreneurship' is innovating in nature. The most significant feature of entrepreneurship is gap filling.

A Function of Status Withdrawal

According to Hagen, 'creative innovation' or change is the fundamental feature of economic growth. In contrast to such 'authoritarian personality' Hagen visualized an "innovative personality". Creative personalities emerge when the members of some social groups experience "the withdrawal of status respect".

A Function of Social, Political And Economical Structure

In his theory of entrepreneurial supply, Kunkel argues that marginality does not generate entrepreneurship and there must be some additional factors at work. Entrepreneurs are not equally distributed in the population. Minorities (religious, ethnic, migrated, displaced elites) have provided most of the entrepreneurial talent. But all the minorities are not important sources of entrepreneurship.

Qualities of Successful Entrepreneur

Several researches have been carried out to identify the traits of true entrepreneur. McClelland points out in his book 'achieving society' that successful entrepreneurs are characterized by: (a)

an unusual creativeness;(b) a propensity of risk-taking and (c) a strong need for achievement. A distillation from fifty research studies reveals the following entrepreneur traits.

1. Total commitment, determination and perseverance
2. Drive to achieve and grow
3. Opportunity and goal orientation
4. Taking initiative and personal responsibility
5. Persistent problem-solving
6. Realism and a sense of humour
7. Seeking and using feedback
8. Internal locus of control
9. Calculated risk taking and risk seeking
10. Low need for status and power
11. Integrity and reliability.

Types of Entrepreneur

In the initial stages of economic development, entrepreneurs tend to have less initiative and drive. As development proceeds, they become more innovating and enthusiastic. Similarly, when entrepreneurs are humble the environment is underdeveloped. Business environment becomes healthy and developed when entrepreneurs are innovating. In a study of American agriculture, Dayhop has classified entrepreneurs in the following categories’.

Innovating Entrepreneurs

Innovative entrepreneurship is characterized by aggressive assemblage of information and the analysis of results derived from sound combination of factors. Persons of this type are generally aggressive in experimentation and cleverly put attractive possibilities into practice. An innovating entrepreneur sees the opportunity for introducing a new technique or a new product or a new market. He or she may raise money to launch an enterprise assemble the various factors, choose top executives and set the organization going.

Adoptive or Imitative Entrepreneurs

This kind of entrepreneurs is ready to adopt successful innovations created by innovative entrepreneurs. Instead of innovating the changes themselves, they just imitate the technology and techniques innovated by others. Such entrepreneurs are particularly important in underdeveloped countries because they contribute significantly to the development of such economies. Imitative entrepreneurs are most suitable for the underdeveloped nations because in these nations people prefer to imitate the technology, knowledge and skill already available in more advanced countries.

Fabian Entrepreneurs

Entrepreneurs of this type of very cautious and skeptical while practicing change. they have neither the will to introduce new change nor the desire to adopt new methods innovated by the most enterprising entrepreneurs. Such entrepreneurs shy and lazy. Their dealings are determined by custom, religion, tradition and past practices. They are not much interested in taking risk and they try to follow the footsteps of their predecessors.

Drone Entrepreneurs

Drone entrepreneurship is characterized by a refusal to adopt and use opportunities to make change in production. Such entrepreneurs may even suffer losses but they do not make changing in production methods. They are laggards as they continue to operate in their traditional way and resist change. They are conventional in the sense that they stick to conventional products and ideas.

Individual and Intuitional Entrepreneurs

In the small scale sector individual entrepreneurs are dominant. Small enterprises outnumber the large ones in every country. Such entrepreneurs have the advantages of flexibility, quick decision making and state patronage.

Entrepreneurs By Inheritance

At times, people become entrepreneurs when they inherit the family business in India; there are a large number of family controlled business houses. Firms in these houses are passed from one generation to another.

Technologist Entrepreneurs

With the decline of the joint family business and the rise of scientific and technical institutions, technically qualified persons have entered the field of business. Their main asset is technical expertise. They raise the necessary capital and employ experts in financial, legal, marketing and areas of business.

Forced Entrepreneurs

Many persons become entrepreneurs on account of the circumstances. They money lenders of yesteryears enter into business due to decline of money lending business with the growth of banking and government legislation.

Field of Entrepreneurial Practice

Understanding the entrepreneurial person creates a challenging problem for academic researchers, there is thus generally no accepted definition or model of what the entrepreneur is or does. At one level, there does not seem to be a problem: We have a category of people who carry out specific functions, broadly labelled 'enter-prize', so what they do can be labelled 'entrepreneurship'. The problem arises when we ask what precisely is this range of functions, because these are variously interpreted. Indeed, Parkinson and Haworth (2008) recently argued that the only consensus seems to be about what entrepreneurship is not: a static entity that is the preserve of elite individuals with special personality traits or characteristics. Instead, a multifaceted, dynamic understanding of entrepreneurship is emerging that presents challenges to research, breaks with functionalist positivism and calls for constant review of epistemological and ontological presumptions (Fletcher, 2006). Of course, it is possible to argue that this does not really matter. From a practical point of view, all we need to know is not what 'it is'. But rather to know what it does and how it works. So we may thus please ourselves in defining or delimiting what it is that we are examining. Yet a primary requirement of most academic research is to define the subject being considered. We are entreated always to 'cover our flanks' with a definition: to fail to do so is academically reckless. It leaves our arguments open to criticisms of imprecisions and looseness of thoughts. But in spite of this shibboleth, more than two decades of concentrated endeavor have failed to produce a universally acceptable definition of entrepreneurship.

Scope of Entrepreneurial Practice:

The broad scope of today's health sector allows for a wide range of activities in which nurses may potentially become professionally self-employed and expert. Basically, nursing entrepreneurship involves nurses owning and selling, for example, the following products and / or services:

- Nursing services
- Development assessment and sale of health care products and devices.
- Health care / policy consultation
- Legal services
- Health care / policy publication.

In this handbook, the focus is on the nurse entrepreneur providing direct nursing services, with the understanding that entrepreneurship must adopt to the legislative, financial and political realities and expectations of the country, province or locality- major factors that influence the emergence of nurse entrepreneurship are the health sectors specific professional regulations and financial policies, and whether health care is a public or a private service or a combined public and private service. The development, scope of practice and regulation of nurse entrepreneurs will therefore largely depend on the economic infrastructure and policies implemented at the national, regional and / or local levels. The variations of nurse entrepreneur practice, reimbursement systems and regulations are as numerous as the different contexts within which they evolve.

Conclusion

It is unanimously felt that there is a greater need for growth of entrepreneurship in the state of Orissa for its economic development. The government can frame policies and programmes to provide all the necessary facilities to attract the educated youths of the state to the fold of industrial entrepreneurship. But, the educated youths themselves have to bear the responsibility. If they lack enterprising spirit and a deep sense of involvement, nothing can help them. The people of Orissa have already proved their worth by entering into business enterprises and have also succeeded on a limited scale. There is a need for an improvement in both quantity and quality of entrepreneurship in the state. This can be done by a little self-confidence and concerted efforts of various institutions giving encouragement and incentives to educated youths of the state. In the era of liberalization and globalization with advancement of information technology, the educated youth of Orissa can make their presence felt in the field of industry and business and can contribute towards state's development

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